

HERCCULES
full CCUS chain demonstration

DETAILED REGIONAL PROFILES

Deliverable D8.2

Date: June 30, 2024

Funded by
the European Union

Funded by the European Union. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101096691. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Deliverable title	Detailed Regional Profiles
Work Package	WP8
Lead beneficiary	Fraunhofer ISI (FRAU)
Due Date	30/06/2024
Actual delivery date	27/06/2024
Dissemination level	Public
Abstract	D8.2 provides contextual information on the two regions where the pilot CO ₂ storage activities in the HERCCULES project are taking place: Emilia-Romagna in Italy and Kavala/Thasos in Greece. This includes the definition of the affected regions along political, administrative and geographical dimensions, as well as stakeholder and public perceptions of CC(U)S.
Project Acronym	HERCCULES
Project Call	HORIZON-CL5-2022-D3-01-15
Type of Action	HORIZON EUROPE - Innovation Actions
Project Start Date	01/11/2023
Project duration	60 months
Grant Number	101096691

Disclaimer

Funded by the European Union. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101096691. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

VERSION	DATE	MODIFICATION	PREPARED BY (Main contributors)	APPROVED BY
1	31.05.2024	Initial version	FRAU - Anne Kantel - Hannah Janßen	FRAU (Elisabeth Dütschke, Sven Alsheimer); ClustER (Elisa Guasti, Francesco Martinelli, Katia Ferrari); CRES (Petros Tzaos, Konstantinos Patlitzianas, Markos)

HERCCULES

full CCUS chain demonstration

				Damasiotis, Vasiliki Polyzoi); and EUCORE (Martina Fantini)
2	27.06.2024	Final version	FRAU - Anne Kantel - Hannah Janßen	

1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This HERCCULES WP8 deliverable on Social Perception and Community Engagement reports on the understanding of the socio-economic and political-administrative contexts of the two regions around the offshore CO₂ storage sites proposed within the project for Italy and Greece. WP8 focuses on public acceptance and community engagement assessing both social perceptions and acceptance of Carbon Capture, Utilisation and Storage (CCUS) technologies in Italy and Greece, and the regulatory, administrative and socio-economic contexts in the two selected study regions within the country. The deliverable is one of the outputs of the exploratory phase of WP8. This exploratory phase serves as a baseline for subsequent project activities, which will deepen the engagement with public stakeholders and aim to derive and implement community engagement strategies. This deliverable builds on the assessment of the regulatory and policy context outlined in D8.1 and is closely linked to the analysis of public perceptions through the implementation of representative surveys at regional and national level in Italy and Greece, the results of which are published in D8.3 of the HERCCULES project.

This report focuses on two regions in the HERCCULES countries, Italy and Greece: the region of and around Kavala/Thasos in Greece and the region of Emilia-Romagna in Italy. Through the triangulation of different qualitative social science research methods, such as the analysis of secondary literature, reports and policies, a media analysis (social and press) and qualitative stakeholder interviews, this deliverable assesses CCUS narratives and stakeholder perceptions within the larger administrative, socio-economic and cultural context of the two study regions.

We find that the regions of Kavala in Greece and Emilia-Romagna in Italy have significant differences in their economic, political and social landscapes that influence their respective attitudes towards CCUS technologies. While Kavala is characterised by a rural economy with a GDP per capita that lies below the national average and an economy dependent on agriculture, fisheries and tourism as well as a significant contribution from the fossil fuel industry to its regional economic development, Emilia-Romagna is one of the most industrialised and prosperous regions in Europe, with high employment rates.

However, the CCUS narratives are similar in both countries, focusing on decarbonisation benefits and economic development, albeit to a different extent and with slightly different levels of awareness and stakeholder engagement in Italy and Greece. Stakeholder awareness and media discourse are more developed in Emilia-Romagna than in Kavala/Thasos, as indicated by slightly more knowledgeable stakeholders and a higher number of articles on the topic in social and print media raising awareness of the technology. Despite potentially broader support in Emilia-Romagna, there appears to be an ongoing conflict between proponents of CCUS, who emphasise its importance for carbon reduction, and environmental groups, who criticise it as 'greenwashing'. The CCUS narrative in Kavala/Thasos, as well as Greece in general, can be characterised as one that focuses on economic development (and job creation). These findings can be interpreted in light of the quantitative survey results presented in D8.3, which show higher levels of CCUS acceptance in Italy than in Greece.

Table of Contents

1	EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	4
2	INTRODUCTION	8
3	BACKGROUND AND METHODS	9
3.1	AFFECTED REGIONS	9
3.2	PUBLIC AND STAKEHOLDER PERCEPTIONS	10
3.3	METHODS	11
3.3.1	DOCUMENT ANALYSIS	12
3.3.2	MEDIA ANALYSIS	13
3.3.3	STAKEHOLDER INTERVIEWS	18
4	RESULTS: REGIONAL COMMUNITY PROFILES	19
4.1	GREECE: KAVALA/ THASOS REGIONAL PROFILE	19
4.1.1	SOCIO-ECONOMIC STRUCTURE AND GEOGRAPHY	19
4.1.2	ADMINISTRATIVE AND POLICY PROFILE	21
4.1.3	CCUS PUBLIC STAKEHOLDERS	21
4.1.4	CCUS NARRATIVES/PERCEPTIONS	22
4.2	ITALY: EMILIA-ROMAGNA REGIONAL PROFILE	23
4.2.1	SOCIO-ECONOMIC STRUCTURE AND GEOGRAPHY	23
4.2.2	ADMINISTRATIVE AND POLICY PROFILE	25
4.2.3	CCUS PUBLIC STAKEHOLDERS	26
4.2.4	CCUS NARRATIVES/PERCEPTIONS	27
5	DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS: COMPARISON OF REGIONAL PROFILES	29
6	CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK	31
7	REFERENCES	32
8	ANNEX: REPORTING TEMPLATES	37
8.1	DOCUMENT ANALYSIS: REPORTING TEMPLATE	37
8.2	MEDIA ANALYSIS REPORTING TEMPLATES	43
8.3	STAKEHOLDER INTERVIEWS: SUMMARY REPORT TEMPLATE	45

Figures and Tables

Figure 1: Location of HERCCULES CO ₂ storage sites	10
Figure 2: Overview of qualitative methods used for this report	12
Figure 4: Number of relevant social media posts by the selected stakeholders over time	18
Figure 5: Location of HERCCULES CO ₂ storage site in Greece	20
Figure 6: Location of HERCCULES CO ₂ storage site in Italy	24
Figure 7: CCUS publications by region (2016-2023) in Italy	28
Figure 8: News coverage on the topic of CCUS in Italy and Greece over time (2016-2023)	30
Table 1: Topics studied in the document analysis	12
Table 2: Search keywords for LexisNexis newspaper search	14
Table 3: Top 5 news publishers (= outlets with the most articles on CCUS) in Italy and Greece from 2016-2023	15
Table 4: Search terms used in Google and YouTube analysis	15
Table 5: Number of stakeholders selected for the social media analysis	16
Table 6: Number of relevant posts by source and keyword	17
Table 7: Number of interviews for the different stakeholder categories	18
Table 8: Greek CCUS stakeholder groups (with examples)	22
Table 9: Italy CCUS stakeholder groups (with examples)	26

List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	
AIA	Integrated Environmental Authorization
ARPAE	Regional Agency for Prevention, Environment and Energy of Emilia-Romagna
CCUS	Carbon capture, utilisation, and storage
CCU	Carbon capture and utilisation
CCS	Carbon capture and storage
EfW	Energy-from-Waste
ETS	Emissions Trading Scheme (ETS)
EU ETS	EU Emission Trading System
HERAMA	Hellenic Hydrocarbons and Energy Resources Management Company
IEA	International Energy Agency
ICHESE	International Commission on Hydrocarbon Exploration and Seismicity in the Emilia Region
ISPRIA	Italian National Institute for Environmental Protection and Research

HERCCULES

full CCUS chain demonstration

IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
MASE	Ministero dell'Ambiente e della Sicurezza Energetica, i.e, Ministry of Environment and Energy Security
NGO	Non-governmental organisation
OSPAR	Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment of the North-East Atlantic
PNIEC	Integrated National Energy and Climate Plan
VIA	Environmental Impact Assessment

2 INTRODUCTION

Carbon Capture, Utilisation, and Storage (CCUS) is recognised by the IPCC (2014) and the IEA¹ as critical for climate change mitigation. Hard-to-abate industries, such as cement and waste-to-energy, which lack cost-effective CO₂ abatement alternatives, are increasingly adopting CCUS (Gallego Dávila et al., 2023), and while the techno-economic case for CCUS is fairly clear, as it is aligned with climate objectives, and currently high on the political agenda with ambitious targets set by national governments and the EU (European Commission, 2024), the nascent policy framework is still evolving (Dütschke & Duscha, 2022) and issues of public support and societal legitimacy remain largely unresolved. A decade ago, CCS was primarily discussed as a means to decarbonise coal-based electricity, driven by the implementation of the EU Emissions Trading Scheme (ETS). Interest in CCS waned with the rise of renewables and low ETS prices, coupled with local opposition and slow policy adaptation, leading to a sharp decline in CCS initiatives, which, however, are now resurfacing within the context of renewed urgency to address the challenge of industrial carbon emissions.

The application of CO₂ capture, use and storage technologies currently appears essential to achieve carbon neutrality by 2050, as outlined in European Directives (e.g. CCS Directive 2009/31/EC) and Commission Recommendations (European Commission, 2024). HERCCULES aims to establish a new, integrated, and replicable approach for the implementation of the full CCUS chain in two strategic circular economy sectors – cement and energy-from-waste (EfW) – in Italy and Greece, where the industrial potential of CCUS remains largely unexplored.

This study assesses public and stakeholder perceptions and narratives used around CCUS by public media and public stakeholders (i.e. policy, industry, civil society and media) within the larger political administrative and socio-economic context of the two regions studied in the HERCCULES project: Emilia-Romagna in Italy and Kavala/Thasos in Greece. The interest in assessing public and stakeholder perceptions of CCUS stems, firstly, from the need to understand society's readiness to adopt these technologies as part of the green energy transition efforts in the two countries in particular and the EU in more general. A recent scenario study by van der Zwaan et al. (2022) underlines this motivation and shows how lack of acceptance, a concept closely related to public perception, can slow down the diffusion of a CCUS pathway. Secondly, the involvement of stakeholders (including citizens) should be part of good democratic practice, especially considering that many ongoing CCUS projects are the beneficiaries of large amounts of public financial support highlighting the need to allow citizens to (directly or indirectly) participate in decision-making and implementation processes. This deliverable is closely linked to HERCCULES Deliverable 8.3, which examines public acceptance at the regional level and the national level.

According to recent studies, public awareness of CCUS technologies is low in almost all European countries (European Commission, 2011; B. Jones, 2012; C. R. Jones et al., 2017; Preuß et al., 2022; Tcvetkov et al., 2019). These low levels of awareness suggest that current perceptions of CCUS are not yet stable, and may change with public debates. Previous studies have documented concerns about CO₂ storage, specifically citing unsuccessful projects in the Netherlands, Poland and Germany (Oltra et al., 2012). However, few studies have focused on Italy (Mabon et al., 2013) and Greece (Mendrinou et al., 2022; Pietzner et al., 2011), and, to our knowledge, none have examined the specific regions of Emilia-Romagna and Kavala/Thasos.

Investigating the regions where CCUS will be most visible to the public is crucial, as the perception of risks and benefits by both the public and relevant stakeholders will significantly influence acceptance (Karytsas et al., 2023). Visibility of CCUS projects can occur at all stages of the value chain, but storage sites (onshore and offshore) are arguably the most visible and therefore often the most critical, in terms of acceptance. Potential local risks include CO₂ leakage, blowouts, induced seismicity, and

¹ <https://www.iea.org/energy-system/carbon-capture-utilisation-and-storage>

impacts on property values or tourism, while benefits could include local economic gains. While these potential risks and benefits may be part of a general public narrative around CCUS, they are often perceived more strongly or differently by people living or working near CCUS infrastructure sites, which has historically led to some opposition to CCS projects (Dütschke, 2010). A recent case study on community acceptance and awareness of CCUS in a Greek community (of unknown location) supports this assessment illustrating that despite low levels of awareness of CCUS technologies, stakeholders would draw on past and situated knowledge to identify potential risks associated with the technology (Stavrianakis et al., 2024). Similarly, findings from the PilotStrategy and CCUS Strategy projects (two recent Horizon 2020 projects) indicate that stakeholder and public perceptions of CCS in Greece are largely dependent on various interacting national and regional factors (Dütschke, Alsheimer, Bertoldo, et al., 2022; Oltra et al., 2020). In a survey study in several European countries, including Greece and Italy, Karytsas et al. (2023) find that local acceptance of CCS is related to, among other things, procedural and distributive justice. Justice in this context included, for example, whether affected local citizens are involved and whether local citizens receive a share of the benefits.

Understanding the narratives and perceptions of CCUS at both national and regional levels is therefore essential for the development of effective policy frameworks, infrastructure development and public engagement activities, which - if done correctly - are often associated with higher levels of technology acceptance. The importance of understanding perceptions is also emphasised by Mendrinou et al. (2022), who investigate the level of readiness for CCUS technologies in Greece and recommend identifying stakeholders' interests, attitudes and perceptions to accompany further technological development of CCUS.

This deliverable aims to:

- i. Provide contextual information about the two study regions, Emilia-Romagna and Kavala/Thasos, such as administrative and political institutions and economic and socio-demographic structures relevant for understanding and interpreting the findings on stakeholder perception and acceptance of CCUS activities in the areas;
- ii. identify overarching public (media) narratives on the topic of CCUS and assess the extent to which CCUS is discussed and who is associated with the issue through a relevant stakeholder mapping.

The report is structured as follows: Section 3 identifies the affected regions and outlines the conceptual and empirical approaches used to collect data on the regions and the stakeholders' perceptions of CCUS. Section 4 presents the results of the data collection and analysis and derives regional community profiles. Section 5 compares the findings between the regions and integrates them with some of results from the representative surveys conducted in T8.3 of the HERCCULES project and presented in D8.3. Finally, section 6 summarises the main findings and relates them to upcoming activities in terms of citizen and public stakeholder engagement strategies.

3 BACKGROUND AND METHODS

3.1 AFFECTED REGIONS

A 2019 review of the literature on public perception of CCS shows that most attention has so far been paid to aspects related to CO₂ storage, while perceptions related to capture, use and transportation have received limited academic attention (Tcvetkov et al., 2019). HERCCULES approaches the question of feasibility and implementation of CCUS technology along the full CCUS value chain, including capture, use and transport. However, based on interviews conducted within the project consortium, the areas most likely to be affected the most are those, where HERCCULES CO₂ storage

will take place as the storage processes may be most visible to citizens. This is due to the fact that this step is fairly visible to the public and affected stakeholders, as it requires new facilities and new (transport) infrastructure. In addition, evidence from previous research suggests that regional areas close to storage sites may have very differing perspective on CCS projects and the potential impacts on everyday life (Parmiter & Bell, 2020). WP8 of the HERCCULES project therefore focuses on the following regions:

- In Greece, the *Prinos* CCS offshore storage site under development and surrounding municipalities in the Kavala/Thasos area located in the region Eastern Macedonia and Thrace were selected as the study region.
- In Italy, the Ravenna CCS offshore storage facility under development in the region Emilia-Romagna was selected.

The CCS site at Prinos in Greece will use an empty offshore oil field, while the CO₂ storage site at Ravenna will use a depleted offshore gas reservoir. Figure 1 below shows the two regions of Emilia-Romagna in Italy and Eastern Macedonia and Thrace in Greece, as well as the smaller units of the province of Ravenna and the regional units of Kavala and Thasos within these larger regions. HERCCULES offshore CCS sites are shown in red.

Figure 1: Location of HERCCULES CO₂ storage sites

3.2 PUBLIC AND STAKEHOLDER PERCEPTIONS

This deliverable focuses on stakeholder perceptions of CCUS technologies, identifying media and stakeholder narratives used around CCUS to assess how different actors in Italy and Greece might

view CCUS technologies. Public perception encompasses the multiple ways in which individuals interpret and respond to information, events and issues within society. It goes beyond mere opinion polls and involves the dynamic interplay of understanding, choice and social interaction (Dowler et al., 2006). Perceptions are influenced by cultural, social and temporal contexts and evolve through ongoing dialogue and interaction. Beliefs and behaviours are not static, but are shaped by a complex interplay of factors, including trust in authorities and experiences within social frameworks. In this regard, the analytical lens of public and stakeholder perceptions is linked to the concept of 'acceptance' often defined as "a favourable or positive response (including attitude, intention, behaviour and – where appropriate – use) relating to a proposed or in situ technology or socio-technical system, by members of a given social unit (country or region, community or town and household, organization)" (Upham et al., 2015).

Although challenging, it is essential to derive overarching insights from diverse individual perspectives, attitudes, behaviours and beliefs. By triangulating data and methods and contextualising findings within broader studies (see Deliverable 8.3), as well as drawing on existing literature, we can identify significant trends in public and stakeholder perceptions of CCUS in Greece and Italy. These findings serve to guide policy, industry and civil society in their efforts to effectively engage with society in the future. In this deliverable, public perceptions of CCUS technologies refer to the beliefs and opinions about CCUS technologies that exist among public stakeholders (such as the media, industry, policy, and civil society). This may include stakeholders who are already interested in, engaged with or somewhat affected by the technology (or not). More general public perceptions of citizens (who may also be stakeholders) are assessed and analysed in D8.3.

3.3 METHODS

The deliverable builds on some existing studies in the literature assessing perceptions of CCUS technologies in Italy and Greece, as well as primary empirical data collected for this report. While the analysis in the related deliverable 8.3 is based on a quantitative dataset of representative household surveys in the two countries of Italy and Greece, the regional country profiles presented here are empirically based on data obtained through the implementation of three different qualitative methods, namely a document analysis, a media survey and stakeholder interviews (see Figure 2: Overview of qualitative methods used for this report). The aim of these methods is to get to know the regions in detail and to contextualise the findings in terms of public and stakeholder knowledge and perceptions of CCS and CCUS. The research design was guided by previous project experience and literature on participation and engagement around (mostly) CCS (Dütschke, Alsheimer, Bohn Bertoldo, et al., 2022; Parmiter & Bell, 2020). The data collection was designed and prepared by FRAU with the support of the local partners (Cluster and EuCore for Italy and CRES for Greece). The preparation included the provision of instructions and reporting templates. Data collection was carried out by the country partners Cluster (supported by EuCore) for Italy and CRES for Greece. Data analysis and interpretation was carried out by FRAU with support from Cluster and CRES.

In the following, the term CCUS is used to refer to both processes (CCUS and CCS). Data collection and analysis often explicitly distinguished between CCUS and CCS, but no major differences were found for the purposes of this study.

Figure 2: Overview of qualitative methods used for this report

3.3.1 DOCUMENT ANALYSIS

Based on desk research and secondary sources, the aim of the qualitative document analysis was to gain initial insights into the industrial, cultural, social, political and economic background of the two different regions.

Based on the definition of the regions concerned (see section 4.1), the aim was to research and analyse existing documents in order to characterise and understand the regions more thoroughly. In order to support and harmonise the research in the two countries, a deductive research approach was chosen. Therefore, themes and questions were identified and defined to guide the subsequent process of searching and selecting existing documents. To this end, a template containing the themes and guiding questions was developed and used to both collect and report the relevant information.

The document analysis aimed to gather information on the following topics:

- (1) Geographical factors and site characteristics
- (2) Governance of the region and administrative factors
- (3) Socio-demographic factors
- (4) Perceptions of CCUS
- (5) Key actors

Table 1: Topics studied in the document analysis

Topic	Sub-category
(1) Geographical factors and location characteristics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • geographic make-up of the region

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Protected areas • Culture • Location characteristics • Seismic activity • Economy • Industry • Unique selling point for the selection as CO₂ storage site
(2) Governance of the region and administrative factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Administration • Political parties • Governance of decarbonisation and CCUS
(3) Socio-demographic factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Population • Employment • Housing • Education
(4) Perceptions of CCUS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Perception of CCUS • Perception decarbonisation • Perceptions of companies involved in CO₂ storage • Perception of risks
(5) Key actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Administration/ governance • Economy • Research and universities • Other key actors

Secondary data sources used include:

- Websites and reports of different stakeholders (e.g. local companies, NGOs)
- Official websites and reports by policymaking and administrations (e.g. EU level, on the regional level)
- Socio-economic reports and statistics

The template was used to document the results of the document analysis in one report per country. This also ensured transparency of the research process and proper documentation of sources and materials used. The template also served as a guide for the analysis. Not all of the pre-selected categories could be covered by the document analysis, underlining the importance of using different methods of data collection to gain a more thorough picture of the two regions.

3.3.2 MEDIA ANALYSIS

Analysis of media sources is a useful method for assessing national and regional public discourse on Carbon Capture, Utilization, and Storage (CCUS) (Snelson, 2016). By systematically examining different media sources, such as print and online newspapers, online news portals, and social media platforms, researchers can identify dominant themes, narratives, and sentiments around CCUS. For

this report, a mix of deductive and inductive content analysis methods was used, that is, what Kuckartz describes as structured, qualitative content analysis (Kuckartz, 2018). This approach allows for some preliminary insights into how cultural, economic and political contexts can shape perceptions and discussions of CCUS. In addition, media analysis can reveal the influence of key stakeholders, including government agencies, industry representatives, and environmental organisations, on public discourse. This method can provide insights into public awareness, acceptance and opposition to CCUS, providing critical information for policymakers and stakeholders seeking to develop effective communication and engagement strategies. The media analysis conducted for this report consists of three parts: (1) a press media analysis, (2) a Google and YouTube analysis, and (3) a stakeholder-driven social media analysis.

The choice of methods and focus of media sources for this analysis was guided by the Reuters Institute Digital News Report 2022, which reports a very high level of use of online media sources (including social media) for Greece. Almost 90% of the population consume their media through the (at least occasional) use of online media, while only 21% use print media, such as printed newspapers. Facebook and YouTube are among the most popular social media and messaging services in the country. In Italy, 75% of the population use online media, including social media, as a source of news and only 15% use print media. Similar to Greece, Facebook and YouTube are the top social media sources in Italy (Newman et al., 2023). Although the proportion of the population that reads print media is limited, it was included in the study for two reasons. First, print media has long been associated with credibility and authority and can therefore have a significant impact on public narratives. Second, a significant proportion of print media also offer online access to some of their articles, blurring the distinction between print and online media sources.

First, a press media analysis of both print and online media sources in Greece and Italy was used to both identify dominant narratives and perceptions of CCUS in the two countries and to compile a list of relevant stakeholders. This was done by conducting a LexisNexis² search using pre-identified keywords in Greek and Italian (see Table 2: Search keywords for LexisNexis newspaper search). The search period was limited to include newspaper articles and online news from January 2016 to December 2023 in Italy and Greece. This allows the analysis to cover the period after the 2015 Paris Agreement on climate change mitigation, adaptation and finance, and to identify any changes in the coverage of CCUS issues over the eight-year period.

Table 2: Search keywords for LexisNexis newspaper search

English	Italian	Greek
CCS	CCS	CCS
CCUS	CCUS	CCUS
CARBON DIOXIDE CAPTURE	CATTURA ANIDRIDE CARBONICA	ΔΕΣΜΕΥΣΗ ΔΙΟΞΕΙΔΙΟΥ ΤΟΥ ΑΝΘΡΑΚΑ
CARBON DIOXIDE STORAGE	STOCCAGGIO ANIDRIDE CARBONICA	ΑΠΟΘΗΚΕΥΣΗ ΔΙΟΞΕΙΔΙΟΥ ΤΟΥ ΑΝΘΡΑΚΑ
CCUS + [municipality name]	CCUS RAVENNA	N/A
CO₂ reduction	RIDUZIONE CO ₂ (+ CCS or CCUS)	ΜΕΙΩΣΗ ΔΙΟΞΕΙΔΙΟΥ ΤΟΥ ΑΝΘΡΑΚΑ (+ CCS or CCUS)
Carbon Sequestration	SEQUESTRO CO ₂	ΑΠΟΜΑΚΡΥΝΣΗ ΔΙΟΞΕΙΔΙΟΥ ΤΟΥ ΑΝΘΡΑΚΑ
CO₂ Cement	CO ₂ CEMENTO	ΔΙΟΞΕΙΔΙΟ ΤΟΥ ΑΝΘΡΑΚΑ ΑΠΟ ΒΙΟΜΗΧΑΝΙΕΣ ΤΣΙΜΕΝΤΟΥ

² LexisNexis is an American data analytics company based in New York City, offers various databases accessible through online portals, including newspaper searches. It offers the world's largest electronic database for legal and public records information.

High Emissions Industry	INDUSTRIE ALTE EMISSIONI	ΒΙΟΜΗΧΑΝΙΕΣ ΥΨΗΛΩΝ ΕΚΠΟΜΠΩΝ
--------------------------------	--------------------------	-----------------------------

Using the above keywords for the search, 391 articles were extracted and identified as relevant to Italy over the eight-year period with very limited coverage in the years 2016-2018 and a significant increase of coverage from 2019 onwards. In Greece, the results of the LexisNexis press analysis are quite different from those in Italy. Using the same keywords (in Greek), a LexisNexis search identified a total of 74 newspaper articles or online news published in Greece (and in Greek) between 2016 and 2023, all of which were published in 2023. One of the reasons for this could be the LexisNexis search method: it could have been possible that the database does not cover Greek news articles in the years before 2023. Therefore, we conducted an alternative search for the term "climate change" ("κλιματική αλλαγή") in the period from 2016 to 2023, which shows dozens and hundreds of articles found in all years, indicating that Greek news articles are included in LexisNexis before 2023 and that CCUS as a topic is simply a very new one in the Greek media discourse.

Table 3: Top 5 news publishers (= outlets with the most articles on CCUS) in Italy and Greece from 2016-2023 provides an overview of the most relevant publishing outlets in both Greece and Italy during the period of analysis.

Table 3: Top 5 news publishers (= outlets with the most articles on CCUS) in Italy and Greece from 2016-2023

Italy	Greece
ANSA (news agency)	Energia gr. (Webnews)
Il Resto del Carlino (regional newspaper)	Ta Nea Online (Webnews)
La Nazione (regional newspaper)	Euro2day (Webnews)
Il Giorno (regional newspaper)	Reporter gr. (Webnews)
Corriere della Sera (national newspaper)	EMEA Business Monitor (Webnews)

After an initial descriptive analysis of the data extracted from LexisNexis, a subsequent qualitative analysis of selected articles was carried out. Based on a prior categorisation, i.e. including the time covered from 2016-2023, excluding articles that were published in more than one outlet, and selection criteria to cover a range of publication sources, approximately 30% of the articles identified for Italy and Greece respectively were randomly selected for subsequent in-depth review. This resulted in a total of 20 articles for the qualitative review for Greece and a total of 39 articles for Italy. Since the news articles were published in Greek or Italian, they were qualitatively coded by ClustER (Italy) and CRES (Greece) to identify (a) themes and narratives through which CCUS is discussed and (b) stakeholders that were mentioned in the context of CCUS such as companies, research institutions, and NGOs. The results of the qualitative review of the press analysis are reported and discussed in section 5.

Second, as part of the overall media analysis for this report, a country-specific search was conducted on Google and YouTube. The search in Italy was conducted in the last week of February 2024 and the search in Greece in the last week of March 2024. Although there is a one-month gap between the searches, we could not identify any major developments internationally or within the two countries studied that took place between the two searches and that could potentially impact the analysis. We focus on interpreting the results within each country indicating the narratives of CCS and CCUS within each of the two countries on their own. The YouTube and Google searches were conducted using the following keywords and combinations:

Table 4: Search terms used in Google and YouTube analysis

English	Italian	Greek
CCUS	CCUS	CCUS
Carbon Capture and Storage	Cattura e stoccaggio carbonio	Δέσμευση και Αποθήκευση Άνθρακα
CCUS + risks	CCUS + benefici	Κίνδυνοι Δέσμευσης και Αποθήκευσης Άνθρακα
CCUS + benefits	CCUS rischi	Οφέλη Δέσμευσης και Αποθήκευσης Άνθρακα
CCUS + [country name]	CCUS Italia	CCUS Ελλάδα

The search was carried out by the HERCCULES partners, CRES and ClustER based in Greece and Italy respectively using the following parameters:

- Use of Google Chrome
- Use of an incognito window,
- History clearing before search
- Clearing cookies before each search

For both the Google and the YouTube analysis, only the first page of the results was reported and analysed in order to identify overall narratives of CCUS as a topic of discourse. The results of the qualitative review of the press analysis are reported and discussed in section 5.

Third, a stakeholder-driven social media analysis was conducted. The aim was to gain further information on how CCUS is discussed in the regions, including the identification of recurring or dominant themes, and to examine how CCUS is framed in posts. Social media was added as a third part of the media analysis, as it is an important source of news in both countries. According to the Reuters Digital News Report already mentioned above (Newman et al., 2022), 71% of respondents in Greece and 47% of respondents in Italy reported using social media as source of information for news in 2022. As social media sources Facebook and LinkedIn were chosen. Facebook was selected as it is the top social media platform in Greece and Italy (Newman et al., 2022). LinkedIn was added because it is an important communication platform for stakeholders such as companies.

In terms of procedure, a stakeholder-driven approach was adopted: social media posts related to CCUS by previously identified stakeholders were analysed, as the main interest of this subtask is to understand the positions of public stakeholders. In a first step, stakeholders identified in the previous tasks (i.e. document analysis and press analysis) were collected (e.g. companies in the region working in fields connected to CCUS, environmental NGOs and science/academia) and, subsequently, the availability of their social media pages was checked. Where necessary, a selection of stakeholders was made (Italy) to ensure that stakeholders from different categories were represented (including media, science, NGO/community, policymaking/ administration and companies). In Italy, one or two stakeholders were selected for each of the following categories: media, science/academia, NGO/community, policy/administration and business. In Greece, fewer stakeholders were generally identified and only a few stakeholders had social media pages available, including posts on CCUS. Therefore, in Greece all stakeholders that met the criteria were selected (three companies and one stakeholder from academia/research). For an overview of the number of stakeholders selected in both countries, see Table 5: Number of stakeholders selected for the social media analysis.

Table 5: Number of stakeholders selected for the social media analysis

Country	Media	Science/Academia	NGO/ community	Policy/Administration	Industry
---------	-------	------------------	-------------------	-----------------------	----------

Greece	0	1	0	0	4
Italy	2	1	2	1	2

The stakeholders' Facebook and LinkedIn pages (where available) were searched using the search terms "CCS" and "CCUS" for the period between 2016 and 2023. This timeframe was chosen for the same reason as in the press analysis: to include the period after the Paris Agreement. All posts matching the criteria that were published by the stakeholder themselves were retrieved. Posts were checked for relevance in order not to include posts using the words "CCS" and "CCUS" in another context. The analysis of the posts was limited to their content (excluding comments) to ensure that only public accounts were examined and privacy right of individuals were protected. For the analysis, FRAU provided a template for the implementing partners, CRES and ClustER, to write a summary about the overall findings from all posts. The analysis was carried by the HERCCULES partners CRES and ClustER and topics for the analysis included:

- Most frequent /dominant framings;
- potential changes of narratives and framings over time;
- differences of narratives and framing among different stakeholders;
- and potential differences between Facebook and LinkedIn.

As shown in Table 6: Number of relevant posts by source and keyword, nine posts were identified as relevant in Greece (three on Facebook and six on LinkedIn), while 45 posts were selected in Italy (36 on Facebook and nine on LinkedIn). In Italy, for the majority of stakeholders, only posts on Facebook were identified (only one stakeholder communicated via LinkedIn). Facebook seemed to be a relevant social media platform for stakeholders from all categories in Italy (media, NGOs, companies and policymaking/administration). In Greece, on the other hand, the majority of posts was collected on LinkedIn, which is likely due to the fact that four out of the five stakeholders were companies, which seem to use LinkedIn more often for communication purposes.

Table 6: Number of relevant posts by source and keyword

Source	Facebook		LinkedIn		Total
	CCS	CCUS	CCS	CCUS	
Greece	2	1	4	2	9
	3		6		
Italy	30	6	7	2	45
	36		9		

Figure 3: Number of relevant social media posts by the selected stakeholders over time illustrates the number of identified posts over the time period of 2016 and 2023. With regard to Greece, it can be observed that the number of selected posts is relatively low. The majority of the posts included in the analysis were published in 2023 (eight out of nine posts). These were mainly came from companies (eight out of nine posts). For Italy, most of the posts were published in 2020 (eleven posts), in 2021 (eleven posts) and in 2023 (a total of 19 posts). While the majority of posts in 2020 came from research accounts (five posts) and NGO stakeholders (four posts), most posts in 2021 were published by accounts from media stakeholders (seven posts) and NGOs (four posts). In 2023, most of the posts are from companies (18 posts).

Figure 3: Number of relevant social media posts by the selected stakeholders over time

3.3.3 STAKEHOLDER INTERVIEWS

The stakeholder interviews are the third and final method block in the development of the regional profiles. The interviews target representatives from industry, policy/administration, NGO/community, science/academia and media to further assess the level of acceptance, expectations and concerns around CCUS.

Qualitative interviews were conducted in Greek and Italian by the HERCCULES partners CRES, Cluster and EUCORE, either in person (three in Italy), using video calls (nine in Italy), or by phone (six in Greece). The interviews were carried out between February and May 2024. Anonymised summaries of the interviews were written and provided by Cluster and CRES in English as input for this report. Written informed consent was obtained from the interviewees before each interview was conducted.

The interviews were conducted as guided interviews, using a guideline of key questions and topics, while leaving room to adapt the interview to the specific interview situation and stakeholder. The interviews started with introductory information about the project and data protection. The guiding questions in the interviews aimed to gain a deeper understanding of:

- The interviewee's own perception of CCUS (including expectations and concerns)
- The interviewee's perspective on other's perception of CCUS (e.g. how CCUS is talked about in the region)
- The stakeholders involved in the discussions and activities related to CCUS
- The most relevant policies and regulations and possible lack of regulations

In total, six interviews were conducted in Greece and 12 in Italy. Table 7: Number of interviews for the different stakeholder categories gives an overview of the number of interviews in in each country for the different stakeholder categories. The categories were chosen to account for a variety of different perspectives (we are loosely following Düttschke et al. (2019) who mapped relevant actors in the CCUS system). The number of interviews is lower in Greece as it was more difficult to identify knowledgeable stakeholders. In this case, insights from industry and community leaders were replaced by interviews with research/academia representatives.

Table 7: Number of interviews for the different stakeholder categories

Country	Industry	Community / NGOs	Policy/ Administration	Science / Academia	Media
---------	----------	------------------	------------------------	--------------------	-------

Greece	1	0	2	3	0
Italy	3	2	5	1	1

4 RESULTS: REGIONAL COMMUNITY PROFILES

In the following, the findings from the different methodological approaches and sources are consolidated and triangulated to develop two regional profiles for Greece (Kavala/Thasos) and Italy (Emilia-Romagna).

4.1 GREECE: KAVALA/ THASOS REGIONAL PROFILE

The following section focuses on the regions of Kavala and Thasos, as the offshore CO₂ storage site for the HERCCULES pilot project is located at Prinos in the Gulf of Kavala, 18 kilometres south of the mainland (Energean plc, 2024). Where data for the region of Kavala (or the region of Thasos) were not available, data from the higher administrative level (the region of Eastern Macedonia and Thrace) were used.

4.1.1 SOCIO-ECONOMIC STRUCTURE AND GEOGRAPHY

The region of Kavala is a regional unit in the north-eastern part of Greece. It is part of the Region of Eastern Macedonia and Thrace. The capital of the Kavala regional unit is the city of Kavala, which is also host of the principle seaport of Eastern Macedonia (other municipalities in the regional unit of Kavala include Paggaios and Nestos). Thasos is an island in the North Aegean Sea off the port of Kavala. Since administrative reforms in 2011, it forms a separate regional unit within the region of East Macedonia and Thrace but is governed and managed together with Kavala.

The only major city in the region is Kavala with a permanent population of around 56,000 (Census 2021) (Hellenic Statistical Authority, 2024a). The city of Kavala can be considered a more urban area and is home to the largest hospital in the region of Eastern Macedonia, several schools and departments of the International University of Greece (based in Thessaloniki, the second largest city in Greece, some 150km away). However, the rest of the regional unit of Kavala (about 116,000 inhabitants in total), as well as the other municipalities (Thasos, Paggaios and Nestos) in the area have a more rural character (Hellenic Statistical Authority, 2024a). The island of Thasos (Thasos regional unit) has a small population of around 13,000 inhabitants (Hellenic Statistical Authority, 2024a). The area is connected to other parts of Greece by motorway and there are several seaports in the region for passenger and freight transport.

With a gross domestic product (GDP) of 13.854€ per capita in 2021 (Hellenic Statistical Authority, 2024b), the region of Kavala ranks below the Greek national average of 17.058€ per capita (Hellenic Statistical Authority, 2024c). However, it is higher than in other regional units of East Macedonia and Thrace: the average GDP of the region was 12,006€ in 2021 (Hellenic Statistical Authority, 2024b). Unemployment rates are only reported for the higher-level region of Eastern Macedonia and Thrace, which includes the regions of Kavala and Thasos. For this region as a whole, the unemployment rate in total is slightly higher (12,5%) than in Greece in general (11,8%) (Hellenic Statistical Authority, 2023).

The most important economic sectors in terms of employment in Kavala and Thasos are agriculture, forestry and fishing, wholesale, retail trade and public administration jobs (Hellenic Statistical Authority, 2024). Kavala's economy has traditionally relied on the industrial, food processing and agricultural sectors (i.e. tobacco, fisheries), but tourism is also playing an increasingly important role in its socio-economic development (Stylidis & Terzidou, 2014). The Gulf of Kavala is one of the largest

fishing grounds in Northern Greece (Energean plc, n.d.) and professional fishermen mainly from Kavala but also from Thasos fish in the Gulf of Kavala. These sectors coexist with the important oil extraction sector operated by Energean Oil & Gas in the Prinos offshore oil fields in the Gulf of Kavala (Energean plc, 2024). In addition, there are some other quarries and companies belonging to the processing industry (e.g. production of phosphate fertilizers and products based on aluminium and uPVC) (see e.g. Kavala NovaFert, 2023; ΚΕΝΤΡΙΚΗ ΕΝΩΣΗ ΕΠΙΜΕΛΗΤΗΡΙΩΝ ΕΛΛΑΔΟΣ, 2024).

Apart from the economic activities described above, few development projects are taking place in the region of Kavala and Thasos. Regarding the production of renewables on a larger scale, mainly PV has been installed for industry, with one larger project involving five solar parks with a total power of 5,2 MW and energy production of 7,500,000 kWh/year (ELVE SA, 2021).

Figure 4: Location of HERCCULES CO₂ storage site in Greece

Regarding seismic activities, in the past eleven years no activities have been recorded in the Kavala area (Institute of Geodynamics, 2024). When it comes to natural and cultural heritage sites, data from the regional units of Kavala and Thasos were analysed. In the region of Kavala there are several protected areas, especially located in the municipality of Nestos, which contribute to the tourist attractiveness of the area. A larger area, including the coastal regions and a part of the Gulf of Kavala in the area of Prinos is part of the Natura 2000 network (European Environment Agency, 2024; IPSY/EC, 2024). In addition, regions of Kavala and Thasos contain some cultural heritage and historical

monuments, such as a medieval aqueduct in Kavala (Εφορεία Αρχαιοτήτων Καβάλας, 2024). In addition, the coastal area of the region is used for recreation, including several public beach areas (meteo.gr, 2024). During the summer months, the area attracts many tourists who visit the coastal villages and beaches. For example, between May and September, around 620,000 people visit the island of Thasos.

4.1.2 ADMINISTRATIVE AND POLICY PROFILE

The regional units of Kavala and Thasos, which belong to the region of Eastern Macedonia and Thrace, are the location of potential CO₂ storage facilities in the region. However, policymaking on CCUS regulations and legislation takes place at the national level, under the Ministry of Environment and Energy.

Legislation on CCUS in Greece is covered by Ministerial Decision 48416/2037/E.103/2011 (Government Gazette B' 2516/2011), which transposes the CCS Directive 2009/31/EC into Greek law. The existing legislation aims to establish rules, measures, and procedures for the environmentally safe storage of CO₂. It specifies details of the areas where storage is permitted and/or prohibited. A permit (official licence) must be applied for and granted. The permit application must include data and information demonstrating the technical capability, social and environmental assessment and feasibility, and the competence of the exploration operator. A storage permit and operator are required for each storage site, and conflicting uses of the site are prohibited. Access to storage sites and transport networks must be granted in a transparent and non-discriminatory manner, taking into account several parameters, including the possibility for stakeholder engagement. To ensure speedy resolution of disputes related to storage and transport, a Dispute Settlement Commission for the Storage of Carbon Dioxide in Geological Formations has been established as an out-of-court body (EL.IN.Y.A.E., 2024). In April 2022, Law 4920/2022 (Government Gazette A '74/15.04.2022) designated the Hellenic Hydrocarbons and Energy Resources Management Company (HEREMA) as the licensing authority for geological storage of CO₂ storage. HEREMA is a state-owned company, which operates independently as a private-sector economic entity. Its role includes issuing exploration and storage permits and managing rights of the Greek state to store CO₂ and other substances, such as natural gas and hydrogen (European Commission, 2023). For more information on the policy and regulatory context see D8.1.

The political system in Greece is quite centralised, despite the relatively recent establishment of directly elected regional governments, which include a governor and a council responsible for implementing regional development policies. Regional policy in Greece is mainly driven by investments financed by European funds (*Regional Policy for Greece Post-2020*, 2020). The current governing party, Nea Dimokratia, is a conservative/centre-right political party.

4.1.3 CCUS PUBLIC STAKEHOLDERS

The stakeholder landscape around CCUS in Greece, particularly in the region of Kavala and Thasos, seems to be less developed than in other countries, such as Italy (see below). CCUS as an issue as well as possible pilot activities are still at an early stage, which is reflected in the stakeholder scene, which mainly involves governmental bodies. Important governmental entities include the Greek government, the Ministry of Environment and Energy and HEREMA as the governing bodies at the national level, as well as the Regional Governor and the Council of the Region of Eastern Macedonia and Thrace, which are responsible for the implementation of regional development policies.

In addition, research institutes, such as the Department of Management Science and Technology of the International University of Thessaloniki and the Democritus University of Thrace (both based in Kavala), as well as the National Technical University of Athens, are potentially important actors, both for the economic development of the region in general and for specific issues, development and knowledge management of CCUS. Third, industry stakeholders, such as Energean and Titan, are

important stakeholders in advancing the feasibility and development of offshore CO₂ storage. They are also more active in communicating about CCUS (e.g. on social media). Currently, the CO₂ storage project at Prinos (the site of the HERCCULES pilot project in Greece) is still in the permitting phase. Potential stakeholders to be involved in future steps of the project include, but are not limited to, the cement and steel industries (potentially also the paper industry), electricity companies (such as PPC), and transport and shipping companies.

Table 8: Greek CCUS stakeholder groups (with examples)

Policy/Administration	Industry	Science / Academia
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ministry of Energy HEREMA 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Oil and gas industry (e.g. ENERGEAN) Cement, steel, paper industry (e.g. TITAN) Transport and shipping industry 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Universities (e.g. International University of Thessaloniki and Democritus University of Thrace) CERTH

So far, there is limited stakeholder involvement from **civil society and environmental organisations** on issues of CCUS in the region (underlined, for example, by the lack of social media articles identified in our analysis). Known organisations, such as the Association of Old Kavala, EOS Kavala 1933, "The Road of Water" (Wood Water Wild, n.d.) and the Environmental Movement of Thasos (Περιβαλλοντική Κίνηση Θάσου, n.d.), have mostly been in favour of renewable energy or, on the contrary, have been concerned with the conflict between landscape conservation and the development (i.e. encroachment) of renewable energy projects on sites of environmental interest, waste and water pollution and waste management.

4.1.4 CCUS NARRATIVES/PERCEPTIONS

The results of the different research methods used for this report indicate that CCUS is still a very new and little known topic for most stakeholders, which is potentially relevant for the development and implementation of CCUS technologies in the country.

This is reflected in the results of the press analysis, which resulted in a total of 74 articles that were extracted and identified as relevant to Greece (see section 4.1.4 for a detailed description of the methodology). Interestingly, all 74 articles were published in 2023 - and no articles were found for the period 2016-2022 indicating that CCUS is a newly emerging topic in the press discourse in Greece (see Figure 7: News coverage on the topic of CCUS in Italy and Greece over time (2016-2023) in section 6).

Similar conclusions can be drawn from the stakeholder-driven social media analysis, which revealed limited awareness and engagement with the issue. When stakeholders did post about CCUS on social media, the posts were from industry or academic stakeholders, suggesting that CCUS is still very much a **technical niche topic in Greece**. This conclusion is also supported by the results of the press analysis, which shows that most of the news published in Greek (and in Greece) in 2023 on the topic of CCUS came from online news sources, with the Greek online portal Energia.gr taking the lead, publishing 27 of the 74 articles (followed by Reporter.gr, Euro2day and Ta Nea Online). All four news outlets are based in Athens and target audiences specifically interested in energy and the environment. Finally, the stakeholder interviews in Greece support the finding that CCUS has not quite reached the level of public discourse. The policy and (non-CCUS) industry stakeholders interviewed had very limited or no knowledge of the issue or the planned development in Prinos. Stakeholders with knowledge of recent developments came almost exclusively from research institutes.

In terms of the content of existing stakeholder and media discourse on CCUS, stakeholder perspectives derived from qualitative interview findings seem to focus on the **potential for economic development (in combination with employment opportunities)** as well as risk and safety issues related to offshore CO₂ storage. This seems to be at least partly reflected in the narratives used by the public media, which focus on entrepreneurship and investment opportunities, as well as the potential of CCUS technologies to **decarbonise** the country's industry and contribute to climate change mitigation efforts.

Results from the Greek analysis of YouTube and Google searches support the narrative of CCUS as a decarbonisation technology. For example, search results frame CCUS as a solution in the energy transition or as a relevant technology in the fight against climate change. In addition, most of the top search results focus on explaining the technology to a wider audience, seemingly with the aim of raising awareness (e.g. websites or YouTube videos of projects funded by the European Commission, information provided by the International Energy Agency (IEA) as well as private companies). Finally, most of the search results from Greece frame CCUS broadly and without a specific geographical focus, with the exception of a few entries that specifically address the technological development and investment plans for CCUS in Greece.

From a regional perspective, the perception of CCUS seems to be characterised by a very limited awareness of the issue and the potential project in Prinos. There is little regional information available about the proposed CO₂ storage project in Prinos operated by Energean, or if available, it remains unknown to many public stakeholders. Some press has been published on other CCUS projects in the country, such as OLYMPUS (Holcim's European decarbonisation project), run by the HERACLES cement industry (International Cement Review, 2023), and IFESTOS, run by the TITAN group (Ζορμιά, 2023). Both projects were selected to receive funding from the EU Innovation Fund and aim to produce zero/low carbon cement using carbon capture and storage (CCS) technologies (International Cement Review, 2023; Ζορμιά, 2023). Otherwise, decarbonisation activities in the Kavala/Thasos region focus on PV and wind farms, and with the exception of some active environmental organisations, stakeholder sensitivity to decarbonisation efforts in terms of CCUS appears to be quite low.

4.2 ITALY: EMILIA-ROMAGNA REGIONAL PROFILE

For Italy, the following sub-sections will provide a description of the Emilia-Romagna region with a special focus on the city of Ravenna.

4.2.1 SOCIO-ECONOMIC STRUCTURE AND GEOGRAPHY

Emilia-Romagna is located in the north-central part of Italy constituting the country's most industrialised region (Regione Emilia-Romagna, n.d.). Approximately 4,437,000 people live in the region (AdminStat Italia, 2022). The population density of the region is similar to the Italian national average (approximately 198 inhabitants per km²) (OECD, 2022). It is one of the most prosperous and economically developed areas in Europe (OECD, 2022). With a GDP per capita of €36,700 (Statista, 2024d), Emilia-Romagna has a GDP above the Italian average (Italy: €35,700) (Statista, 2024b). The region has an employment rate (70,2%) well above the Italian average (around 60.9%) (Statista, 2023a, 2023b). Incomes are very close to the national average (the average gross annual salary in 2023 was €31,285 in Emilia-Romagna, compared to a national average of around 31,500€) (Statista, 2024a, 2024c).

Overall, the region of Emilia-Romagna is well connected to southern Italy, northern Italy and northern Europe. Bologna, for example, has an airport and is connected to high-speed trains (Regione Emilia-Romagna, n.d.). The University of Bologna, including a campus in Ravenna, is among the top five Italian universities in international rankings (Times Higher Education, n.d.).

Important economic sectors include the automobile and motorcycle industries, food production, ceramic and construction (OECD, 2022). Fossil fuel extraction has a long history in the region with two important extraction areas: Ravenna and Parma-Piacenza (eni, 2022; Ricerche Industriali ed Energetiche, 2015). A large amount of goods are transported through the Port of Ravenna (Regione Emilia-Romagna, n.d.), which is the most important port in Emilia-Romagna, and also the site of the HERCCULES CO₂ storage pilot.

The city of Ravenna is one of the largest cities in Emilia-Romagna (around 156,345 inhabitants in January 2024 (Istat, 2024)), and is located about 80 km from Bologna, the region's capital city. The city centre of Ravenna is 8 km away from the Adriatic Sea and is home to the Port of Ravenna (ART-ER, n.d.). In terms of wellbeing and quality of life, Ravenna is one of the leading cities in Italy, offering excellent health and social services, public transport, higher education and training (Tadini, 2023).

Figure 5: Location of HERCCULES CO₂ storage site in Italy

Emilia-Romagna is affected by “average” seismicity, which is predominantly in Romagna, where the largest earthquakes in the region have occurred in the past (Regione Emilia-Romagna, 2024b). The last seismic emergency occurred in May 2012 (Regione Emilia-Romagna, 2024a). The region has several protected areas, such as the Po Delta Regional Park, located near the city of Ravenna and

bordering the Adriatic Sea (Regione Emilia-Romagna, n.d.). In addition, UNESCO has designated several cities in Emilia-Romagna, including Ravenna, as World Heritage sites, recognising their historical, cultural, artistic, and natural significance (Emilia Romagna Turismo, 2024). For this reason, the Romagna Riviera coastline near Ravenna is very popular with both residents and tourists during the summer with the exception of the industrial area of the port of Ravenna, which includes chemical and petrochemical companies. From an environmental management standpoint, this industrial area can be considered to be located in an ecologically as well as socially "sensitive" territory due to the proximity to the coastline as a tourist and recreational area (Emas Ravenna, n.d.). Emilia-Romagna as a whole is a top European tourist destination, attracting over 11.5 million visitors and generating 50 million overnight stays annually (Regione Emilia-Romagna, 2024c).

4.2.2 ADMINISTRATIVE AND POLICY PROFILE

The city of Ravenna belongs to the region of Emilia-Romagna. The government of the region is the Executive Board, composed of the President, the Undersecretary to the Presidency and 10 Regional Ministers. The Executive Board is proposing legislation. The President and Executive Board are accountable to the Regional Council, which is the region's legislative assembly. Consisting of 50 members, it represents the people in Emilia-Romagna and is monitoring the implementation of laws and approves government programmes and regional budgets (Regione Emilia-Romagna, n.d.). Traditionally, left-wing parties were the strongest political force in the region, however, since 2018 the situation is more competitive between right- and left-wing party coalitions. Currently, the centre-left coalition has the majority of seats in the Regional Council (Regione Emilia-Romagna, 2020), which differs from the national level, as the centre-right has the majority of seats there (Agi.it, 2022).

In Italy, regulations related to decarbonisation and CCUS are partly developed at national level (Ministry of the Environment and Energy Security (MASE)) and partly at regional level (Ministero dell'Ambiente e della Sicurezza Energetica, 2023b). Italy follows international and European agreements and regulations, such as the Paris Climate Agreement, the OSPAR Convention, the EU CCS Directive, the EU ETS and the London Protocol (IEA, 2011). Since 2018, the National Integrated Energy and Climate Plan (PNIEC) sets the national targets for energy efficiency, renewable energy and reduction of CO₂ emissions. In this plan, CCUS is mentioned for the first time at the national policy level in the country (Ministero dell'Ambiente e della Sicurezza Energetica, 2023a). For more information on the policy and regulatory context, see D8.1.

In the context of infrastructure and industrial projects, two procedures are important to ensure compliance with social and environmental requirements: the Valutazione di Impatto Ambientale - Environmental Impact Assessment (VIA) and the Autorizzazione Integrata Ambientale - Integrated Environmental Authorization (AIA). These assessments must be completed and approved by the competent authority before the start of operations or before major changes are made³ in order to comply with the principles of Integrated Pollution Prevention and Control (IPPC) (Assemblea Legislativa della Regione Emilia-Romagna, n.d.; Ministero dell'Ambiente e della Sicurezza Energetica, n.d.).⁴

The Italian public administration is considered "regionalised", with regions and local authorities (metropolitan areas, provinces, and municipalities) responsible for some legislative and administrative tasks not specifically assigned to the State. Collaboration between the State and Regions is facilitated

³ DECRETO LEGISLATIVO 3 aprile 2006, n. 152, <https://www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:decreto.legislativo:2006-04-03;152>

⁴ Northern Italy has some experience with (so far unsuccessful) CCS projects: Porte Tolle was a CCS project by Enel in Proto Tolle, Veneto, Italy. Initiated in 2009, the project was terminated in 2013 due to delays from permitting issues. The environmental impact assessment was annulled by the Italian State Council, leading to Enel requesting the project's termination (Kapetaki et al. 2017).

through the State/Regions Conference (Conferenza Stato/Regioni). However, despite this decentralised structure, Italy's political culture and party system remain highly centralised. In addition, the administrative apparatus has not adapted to the decentralisation of the state in recent decades, resulting in some duplication of bureaucracy (European Committee of the Regions).

4.2.3 CCUS PUBLIC STAKEHOLDERS

Emilia-Romagna is one of the richest and most industrialised regions in Europe, with several governmental stakeholders involved in the development of CCUS activities in the area: These include, at the regional government level, the Regional Agency for Prevention, Environment and Energy of Emilia-Romagna (ARPAE), as the agency responsible for CCS and environmental licensing, the Emilia Romagna Region Administration and the Municipality of Ravenna. The national Ministry for the Environment and Energy Security (MASE) is the legislative body responsible for the CCUS regulatory framework in the country, and the Italian National Institute for Environmental Protection and Research (ISPRA) is a public legal entity that carries out scientific research, monitoring and training activities. Several companies from different industries (e.g. cement, steel, energy, ceramics, chemicals) are also already active or potentially interested and therefore appear as relevant stakeholders with regard to ongoing and future CCUS activities in the region. Many of these companies are already active in the area in and around the Port of Ravenna. In addition, the region is characterised by a strong civil society and environmental non-profit sector that focuses on public engagement in environmental (marine) conservation efforts, but also in starting to engage and communicate on CCS. Finally, the region has an active and influential research sector with several research institutes and universities engaged in research, projects, teaching and informing policy development on CCUS issues. Examples of stakeholders categorised by stakeholder group are listed in Table 9: Italy CCUS stakeholder groups (with examples) below.

Table 9: Italy CCUS stakeholder groups (with examples)

Policy/Administration	Industry	Science / Academia	NGOs/community
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ARPAE • Administration of Emilia Romagna • Municipality of Ravenna • Ministry MASE • ISPRA 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Confindustria Ravenna (Association of industry in Ravenna) • Offshore contractors and engineering services (e.g. Roca, Rosetti Marino SPA, Techfem SPA) Association) • Cement, steel and ceramic industry (e.g. Confindustria Ceramica, Buzzi, Marcegaglia) • Energy industry (e.g. ENI, Enereco SPA, Edison) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CNR – Consiglio nazionale della ricerca (National Research Council) • ENEA – Agenzia nazionale per le nuove tecnologie, l'energia e lo sviluppo economico sostenibile (National Agency for New Technologies, Energy and Sustainable Economic Development) • University of Bologna • RSE – Ricerca sistema energetico 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fondazione Cetacea • Legambiente Emilia Romagna • WWF Emilia Romagna • Greenpeace • Recommon Legambiente Emilia Romagna • "Rete Emergenza Climatica e Ambientale dell'Emilia Romagna (RECA ER)" • Fridays for Future

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Infrastructures (e.g. Snam) • Yara - fertilizers • and other services and commercial sectors (e.g. Hera Ambiente, IREN, Camera di Commercio) 	<p>(Energy system research)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LEAP – Laboratorio Energia Ambiente Piacenza (Laboratory Energy Environment Piacenza) 	
--	--	---	--

4.2.4 CCUS NARRATIVES/PERCEPTIONS

The results of various research methods used in this report indicate that CCUS is gradually becoming a topic of interest among stakeholders in the Emilia-Romagna region. The discussions highlight the potential of these technologies to reduce CO₂ emissions in hard-to-abate industries. However, there is some controversy between political and industrial stakeholders, who support CCUS, and environmental activists, who fear that an emphasis on CCUS could hinder further decarbonisation efforts. Some interviewed stakeholders believe that CCUS remains largely unknown to the general public, and there are concerns that perceptions of potential risks and safety issues, such as earthquakes, might dominate the debate, overshadowing potential benefits as the Emilia-Romagna region has been affected by a seismic emergencies in the past (last in 2012). However, the overall findings from the data do not support the assumption of public concern regarding earthquakes. Instead, the data suggest a generally favourable perception of CCUS technologies among stakeholders, with its decarbonisation potential being a primary focus, both positively and critically. Despite this favourable attitude and a slow increase in interest in CCUS, general stakeholder awareness (similar to the one of the public) remains low.

The LexisNexis press analysis search for Italy supports this observation. While the search yielded a total of 391 articles (including newspaper articles and online news published by international news agencies in Italian and by Italian news agencies in Italian or English), the years 2016 to 2019 are characterised by limited coverage of CCUS as a topic in the Italian news (with an average of 3.75 news items per year during this period). However, coverage of the topic increases after 2020, reaching a total of 179 new articles published on the topic in 2023 (see Figure 7: News coverage on the topic of CCUS in Italy and Greece over time (2016-2023) in section 6) suggesting that - at least in some circles - the topic of CCUS has gained on prominence.

The majority of publications in Italy identified by LexisNexis were published in two different outlets (see also Table 3: Top 5 news publishers (= outlets with the most articles on CCUS) in Italy and Greece from 2016-2023. The first is *Il Resto del Carlino*, an Italian newspaper based in Bologna (and its sister publications *Il Giorno* and *La Nazione*). The second news source, which publishes the majority of articles on CCUS, is the Italian news agency ANSA. Italy's most widely read daily newspaper, *Corriere della Sera*, with a circulation of almost 250,000, also publishes on CCUS issues, but significantly less than *Il Resto del Carlino* (25 news items compared to 101 in the period studied). Most of the newspapers publishing on the subject are located in the Emilia-Romagna region (see Figure 6: CCUS publications by region (2016-2023) in Italy).

Figure 6: CCUS publications by region (2016-2023) in Italy

Thus, the frequency of information about CCUS in the media has increased significantly in recent years, particularly in relation to activities in Emilia-Romagna. This is consistent with the stakeholder interest findings, as the results show some interest and engagement with the issue across all stakeholder groups. The results of the stakeholder-driven social media analysis indicate that interest and engagement in the issue has increased in recent years, particularly among industry stakeholders. However, even among stakeholders, in particular policy and civil society actors, detailed knowledge of CCUS technologies seems to remain limited.

In terms of the content of the existing stakeholder and media narratives on CCUS, **narratives on climate change mitigation and reducing CO₂ emissions for the hard-to-abate industrial sector** seem to be the driving force in favour of the technology. In recent years, the narrative seems to have shifted slightly from a singular focus on decarbonisation in general to more project-related coverage of activities in and around Ravenna, as well as more business-driven concerns about competitiveness and supply chain security.

Decarbonisation is considered important in the Emilia-Romagna region. For example, the city of Bologna has high ambitions to become carbon neutral by 2030 (Comune di Bologna, 2022). There are also several civil society associations that stress the importance of decarbonisation. For example, the Emilia Romagna Climate and Environmental Emergency Network (Rete Emergenza Climatica e Ambientale dell'Emilia Romagna = RECA ER) is a coordination of regional organisations that have decided to join forces to amplify the voice of civil society and social movements concerned about the inadequacy and inconsistency of the response to the climate emergency (Associazione Salvaiciclisti-Bologna, n.d.). Similarly, industry stakeholders and policy actors frame CCUS activities as a pathway to decarbonize hard-to-abate industry sectors by focusing on technical narratives and potential economic benefits.

With several environmental organisations in the region, Emilia-Romagna can be said to have an environmentalist culture. Protests are concentrated in specific areas. For example, there is a large movement against an ongoing regasification project off the coast of Ravenna (Legambiente, 2023). The protest is against the project as a whole, with environmental groups accusing politicians of serving the economic interests of the fossil fuel industry. Recently, the issue of CCUS has also emerged as an environmental and climate-related concern, with some environmental NGOs raising concerns about the technology. WWF and Fridays for Future, for example, claim that the CCUS supply chain is not sufficiently developed for CCUS to play a significant role in meeting the Paris Agreement targets (Spini,

HERCCULES

full CCUS chain demonstration

2023). It is also considered to be associated with exorbitant costs and risks that are difficult to manage (WWF, 2021). Legambiente portrays CCUS as an act of greenwashing that will be used to continue exploiting fossil fuels (e.g. CO₂ emissions from a gas processing plant are to be stored in the Ravenna CO₂ storage facility) (Legambiente Emilia-Romagna, 2022).

Findings from the Italian analysis of YouTube and Google searches seem to support the narrative of CCUS as a decarbonisation technology on the one hand, with some critical voices about greenwashing and risks in the search results on the other. Most of the top search results focus on explaining the technology to a wider audience, seemingly with the aim of broadening awareness (e.g. using documentaries and webinars to talk about 'top 3 carbon capture technologies' on one side of the spectrum and 'risks and illusions of CCUS' on the other). Finally, search results from Italy on Google and YouTube provide a mix of more international and Italian sources.

5 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS: COMPARISON OF REGIONAL PROFILES

The regions of Kavala in Greece and Emilia-Romagna in Italy present stark contrasts in their economic, political and social landscapes, each influencing their approach and perception of carbon capture, utilisation and storage technologies. Kavala, a more rural area far from the industrial and political centres of Greece, relies heavily on agriculture, fishing and tourism, with ENERGEAN as the main fossil fuel industry player in the region making a significant economic contribution. The region's average GDP per capita is significantly lower than the national average, reflecting its economic vulnerability. Kavala is home to the campuses of two major universities, which contribute to local education but do not significantly alter the region's predominantly rural and industrial economy. Politically, Greece operates a more centralised system, with regulatory and licensing decisions, particularly those concerning CCUS, being made in Athens, limiting local influence over such projects.

In contrast, Emilia-Romagna is one of the most industrialised and economically prosperous regions in Europe. Employment rates and incomes here are above the Italian national average, reflecting a robust economy driven by a diverse range of industries. This economic strength translates into a more proactive engagement with CCUS activities, supported by a range of stakeholders already involved or interested in these technologies. Italy's political system, unlike Greece's, is decentralised, giving regional and local authorities a bit more autonomy over administrative functions. This decentralised structure could potentially provide institutional access points for regional stakeholders in Emilia-Romagna to shape public discourse and influence policy and the implementation of technologies such as CCUS more effectively. Despite their economic and political differences, both regions share a dependence on tourism and are home to historical and environmentally protected sites.

Public and stakeholder awareness of CCUS varies between the two regions. In Greece, particularly in and around Kavala and Thasos, stakeholder awareness of CCUS and the potential local implementation of projects in Prinos appears to be low. It was difficult to find relevant regional stakeholders to interview for this report who had (some) awareness of the issue, and stakeholder involvement in the Kavala region seems to be limited to industry/business and academia. Existing stakeholder narratives on CCUS can still be described as a 'technical niche narrative', focusing mainly on the potential for economic development (combined with employment opportunities), with some open questions regarding potential risks and safety issues in local implementation. The media discourse, which in Greece is also still limited to media targeting a specific audience interested in energy and the environment, seems to reflect these stakeholder narratives, but also emphasises the potential of CC(US) technologies to decarbonise the country's industry. However, it is also evident that CCUS is indeed starting to be discussed in Greece (only a few years delayed in comparison to Italy).

In Italy, particularly in the Emilia-Romagna region, stakeholder awareness seems to be slightly higher than in Greece. Various methods used for this report indicate that CCUS is emerging as a topic of interest among several stakeholders in Emilia-Romagna (with an increase in interest over the last three to four years). The existing stakeholder and media discourse on CCUS focuses on climate change mitigation and the reduction of CO₂ emissions in difficult to abate industrial sectors, which is driving support for the technology. The differences in the discourse between Greece (as an emerging niche issue) and Italy (as an issue that has been attracting attention but is now increasingly on the agenda) can also be seen in the figure below, which shows the number of (online) press articles on CCUS over the last few years.

Figure 7: News coverage on the topic of CCUS in Italy and Greece over time (2016-2023)

In recent years, the narrative in Italy has shifted slightly from a singular focus on decarbonisation to more project-related coverage, particularly around activities in Ravenna, as well as economic concerns about competitiveness and supply chain security. One key point highlights the current CCUS narrative in Emilia-Romagna: Conflicts seem to arise between stakeholders, mainly industry and political actors, who promote CCUS technologies as essential to reduce carbon emissions and achieve climate goals, and environmental groups who perceive CCUS as "greenwashing" that allows the oil and gas industry to continue business as usual.

Findings from a HERCCULES representative survey at both national and regional levels in Italy and Greece also indicate low to moderate public familiarity of CCUS (for more information, see D8.3). In Emilia-Romagna, over 44% of respondents have heard of the technology, matching the familiarity level among the general population in Italy. In contrast, there is a more pronounced difference in Greece, with 48% of respondents in Eastern Macedonia and Thrace reporting that they are familiar with the technology, compared with 58% nationally. Interestingly, and slightly different from the qualitative findings of the regional profiles, more respondents in Greece indicated to have had at least heard of CCUS as a technology. However, when it comes to the evaluation of CCUS as an option for climate change mitigation it is evaluated more poorly in Greece than in Italy (after information on the technology was given). Italian respondents tend to evaluate CCUS positively as a climate change mitigation option, with over 70% of valid responses rating it as a good or very good option. This seems to be consistent with the qualitative findings that point towards a strong (albeit somewhat conflictual) narrative of decarbonisation as a benefit of CCUS in Italy, while the current narrative in Greece focuses more on economic (and job) opportunities.

HERCCULES

full CCUS chain demonstration

Finally, the results of the representative surveys indicate that the expected negative impacts of CCUS (i.e. perceived risks, including environmental, social and economic impacts) are a major factor influencing acceptance negatively. At this stage, it is too early to assess whether perceived environmental or social impacts on, for example, tourism in the regions will negatively influence stakeholder and public perceptions in the future.

6 CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

The regions of Kavala in Greece and Emilia-Romagna in Italy have significant differences in their economic, political and social landscapes that influence their respective attitudes towards Carbon Capture, Utilisation and Storage (CCUS) technologies. Kavala, characterised by a rural economy reliant on agriculture, fisheries and tourism, with a significant contribution from the fossil fuel industry, faces economic challenges with a GDP per capita lower than the national average. The region's political environment is centralised, with decisions on CCUS taken in Athens, limiting local influence. Public and stakeholder awareness of CCUS in Kavala is low, and discourse is limited to technical narratives focused on potential economic benefits and job creation, with some concerns about risks and safety.

On the other hand, Emilia-Romagna is one of the most industrialised and prosperous regions in Europe, with high employment rates and incomes. Its decentralised political system gives regional authorities considerable autonomy, facilitating proactive engagement with CCUS activities. Stakeholder awareness and media discourse are more developed in Emilia-Romagna, focusing on climate change mitigation and reducing CO₂ emissions in difficult-to-abate sectors. Despite broader support, there are conflicts between proponents of CCUS, who emphasise its importance for carbon reduction, and environmental groups, who criticise it as 'greenwashing'.

The findings of this report serve as a baseline for the development and implementation of stakeholder and public engagement strategies in the context of the HERCCULES project. As can be seen in this report (as well as in D8.3), some stakeholder and community concerns about CCUS technologies, which are relatively new and sparsely implemented energy transformation measures, remain and could be a barrier to wider stakeholder and public acceptance in the future. Appropriate engagement formats and content specific to the national and regional situation will be developed as part of Tasks 8.4, 8.5 and summarised and made available in Task 8.6.

7 REFERENCES

- AdminStat Italia. (2022). *Maps, analysis and statistics about the resident population: Demographic balance, population and family trends, age classes and average age, civil status and foreigners*. <https://ugeo.urbistat.com/AdminStat/en/it/demografia/dati-sintesi/emilia-romagna/8/2>
- Agi.it (2022, September 27). Il centrodestra ha la maggioranza assoluta dei seggi, 235 deputati su 400 e almeno 112 senatori su 200. *AGI - Agenzia Italia*. <https://www.agi.it/politica/news/2022-09-26/diretta-risultati-elezioni-trionfo-meloni-18211913/>
- ART-ER. (n.d.). *LIFE IN RAVENNA, ITALY*. Retrieved May 29, 2024, from <https://internationaltalents.art-er.it/emilia-romagna-region/ravenna>
- Assemblea Legislativa della Regione Emilia-Romagna. (n.d.). *Documento Demetra » Demetra – Normativa, atti e sedute della Regione Emilia-Romagna*. Retrieved June 20, 2024, from <https://demetra.regione.emilia-romagna.it/al/articolo?urn=er:assemblealegislativa:coll:XI;982>
- Associazione Salvaiciclisti-Bologna. (n.d.). *Patto per il clima e per il lavoro: Chi siamo*. Retrieved May 29, 2024, from <https://pattoperilclimaeperillavoro.it/chi-siamo/>
- Comune di Bologna. (2022). *Bologna tra le 100 città carbon neutral entro il 2030*. <https://www.comune.bologna.it/notizie/bologna-100-citta-carbon-neutral-entro-2030>
- Dowler, E., Green, J., Bauer, M., & Gasperoni, G. (2006). *Assessing public perceptions: issues and methods*. https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Martin-Bauer-2/publication/30528118_Assessing_public_perception_issues_and_methods/links/00b7d530b0ca10e79d000000/Assessing-public-perception-issues-and-methods.pdf
- Dütschke, E. (2010). What drives local public acceptance - comparing two cases from Germany. *Energy Procedia*, 1–7.
- Dütschke, E., Alsheimer, S., Bertoldo, R., Ataberk, B., Delicado, A., Gonçalves, L., Kappler, L., López-Asensio, S., Mays, C., Oltra, C., Poumadere, M., Prades, A., Preuß, S., Rowland, J., & Schmidt. (2022). *Community Acceptance: Findings from community profiles and first local survey*. https://pilotstrategy.eu/sites/default/files/2022-11/PilotSTRATEGY%20Deliverable%206-2-final_211122_clean.pdf
- Dütschke, E., Alsheimer, S., Bohn Bertoldo, R., Delicado, A., Duscha, V., Germán, S., Gonçalves, L., Kappler, L., López-Asensio, S., Mays, C., Oltra, C., Poumadere, M., Prades, A., Preuß, S., Rowland, J., Schmidt, L., & M. L. Veloso, F. (2022). Engaging the Public with CCUS: Reflection on a European Project Approach. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4284094>
- Dütschke, E., & Duscha, V. (2022). Is there a future for CCUS in Europe? An analysis of the policy framework and societal support. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=4286232
- Dütschke, E., Wesche, J., Oltra, C., & Prades, A. (2019). *Stakeholder mapping report (STRATEGY CCUS WP3 Deliverable D3.1)*. https://www.strategyccus.eu/sites/default/files/D3.1_STRATEGY%20CCUS_2019_08_28_StakeholderMappingReport.pdf
- EL.IN.Y.A.E. (2024, May 30). *Y.A. H.Π. 48416/2037/E.103/2011 (ΦΕΚ 2516/Β` 7.11.2011) | ΕΛΙΝΥΑΕ*. <https://www.elinyae.gr/ethniki-nomothesia/ya-ip-484162037e1032011-fek-2516b-7112011>
- ELVE SA (2021, February 8). ELVE Energy. *ELVE SA*. <https://www.elvesa.gr/elve-energy/>

- Emas Ravenna. (n.d.). *DISTRETTO DI RAVENNA - Emas Ravenna*. Retrieved May 29, 2024, from <https://www.emasravenna.it/distretto-di-ravenna/>
- Emilia Romagna Turismo. (2024). *UNESCO World Heritage sites in Emilia-Romagna*. <https://emiliaromagnaturismo.it/en/art-culture/unesco>
- Energiean plc (n.d.). Environmental & social impact assessment (esia) for prinos offshore development project. <https://www.energiean.com/media/1040/esia-chapter-08-environmental-and-social-baseline.pdf>
- Energiean plc. (2024, March 27). *Prinos Concession | Energiean PLC*. <https://www.energiean.com/operations/greece/prinos-concession/>
- eni. (2022). *Settanta e oltre - 1952-2022*. <https://www.eni.com/assets/documents/ita/media/VolumeRavenna-70-DCS.pdf>
- European Commission. (2011). *Special Eurobarometer 364: Public Awareness and Acceptance of CO2 capture and storage*.
- European Commission. (2024, June 2). *Towards an ambitious Industrial Carbon Management for the EU* (COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, THE COUNCIL, THE EUROPEAN ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL COMMITTEE AND THE COMMITTEE OF THE REGIONS No. 62). https://energy.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2024-02/Communication_-_Industrial_Carbon_Management.pdf
- European Committee of the Regions. *Italy - Divisions of Power*. <https://portal.cor.europa.eu/divisionpowers/Pages/Italy-Introduction.aspx>
- European Environment Agency. (2024, March 20). *Natura 2000 Viewer*. <https://natura2000.eea.europa.eu/>
- Gallego Dávila, J., Sacchi, R., & Pizzol, M. (2023). Preconditions for achieving carbon neutrality in cement production through CCUS. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 425. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.138935>
- Hellenic Statistical Authority. (2024a, March 27). *Main Page ELSTAT - ELSTAT*. <https://www.statistics.gr/en/home>
- Hellenic Statistical Authority. (2024b, May 29). *Gross Domestic Product Per Capita (NUTS I NUTS II and NUTS III) / 2021*. <https://www.statistics.gr/en/statistics/-/publication/SEL57/->
- Hellenic Statistical Authority. (2024c, May 29). *Per capita figures: GDP and National Income / 2022*. <https://www.statistics.gr/en/statistics/-/publication/SEL33/->
- IEA. (2011). *Carbon Capture and Storage and the London Protocol*. https://iea.blob.core.windows.net/assets/a0a0ee83-6842-4c28-b64d-a01df895bee8/CCS_London_Protocol.pdf
- Institute of Geodynamics. (2024). *BBNET - Moment Tensors*. <https://bbnet.gein.noa.gr/HL/seismicity/mts/revised-moment-tensors>
- International Cement Review. (2023). *Heracles Group's Olympus CO2 project receives EU funding*. <https://www.cemnet.com/News/story/176039/heracles-group-s-olympus-co2-project-receives-eu-funding.html>
- IPCC (Ed.). (2014). *Climate Change 2014: Synthesis Report: Contribution of Working Groups I, II and III to the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*.
- IPSY/EC. (2024, March 27). *GEODATA.gov.gr - Maps*. <https://geodata.gov.gr/maps/?locale=el>
- Istat. (2024). *Resident population on 1st January : Emilia-Romagna*. <http://dati.istat.it/?lang=en&SubSessionId=611e3eba-9574-4e45-b2fe-39c3ff3ce6e6>
- Jones, B. (2012). *global Status of large scale integrated ccs projects: June 2012 update*. Global CCS Institute.

- Jones, C. R., Olfe-Kräutlein, B., Naims, H., & Armstrong, K. (2017). The Social Acceptance of Carbon Dioxide Utilisation: A Review and Research Agenda. *Frontiers in Energy Research*, 5, 1-13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenrg.2017.00011>
- Kapetaki, Z., Hetland, J., Le Guenan, T., Mikunda, T., & Scowcroft, J. (2017). Highlights and Lessons from the EU CCS Demonstration Project Network. *Energy Procedia*, 114, 5562–5569. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2017.03.1696>
- Karytsas, S., Polyzou, O., Oikonomou, T. I., & Karytsas, C. (2023). A transnational study on the determinants of social acceptance of carbon capture, transport, and storage (CCS). *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, 1196(1), 12092. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/1196/1/012092>
- Kavala NovaFert. (2023). *Kavala NovaFert*. <https://kavalanovafert.com/>
- Kuckartz, U. (2018). *Qualitative Inhaltsanalyse. Methoden, Praxis, Computerunterstützung* (4th ed.). Beltz.
- Legambiente. (2023). *Legambiente domani in piazza a Ravenna contro le false promesse del fossile*. <https://www.legambiente.it/comunicati-stampa/legambiente-domani-in-piazza-a-ravenna-contro-le-false-promesse-del-fossile/>
- Legambiente Emilia-Romagna. (2022). *CCS, stretta di mano ENI-SNAM: facciamo il punto | Legambiente Emilia-Romagna APS*. <https://www.legambiente.emiliaromagna.it/2022/12/20/ccs-stretta-di-mano-eni-snam-facciamo-il-punto/>
- Mabon, L., Vercelli, S., Shackley, S., Anderlucchi, J., Battisti, N., Franzese, C., & Boot, K. (2013). 'Tell me what you Think about the Geological Storage of Carbon Dioxide': Towards a Fuller Understanding of Public Perceptions of CCS. *Energy Procedia*, 37, 7444–7453. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2013.06.687>
- Mendrinou, D., Karytsas, S., Polyzou, O., Karytsas, C., Nordø, Å. D., Midttømme, K., Otto, D., Gross, M., Sprengel, M., Peuchen, R., Geerdink, T., & Puts, H. (2022). Understanding Societal Requirements of CCS Projects: Application of the Societal Embeddedness Level Assessment Methodology in Four National Case Studies. *Clean Technologies*, 4(4), 893–907. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cleantechnol4040055>
- meteo.gr. (2024, March 27). *προγνώσεις καιρού για την Ελλάδα*. <https://www.meteo.gr/beaches-home.cfm>
- Ministero dell'Ambiente e della Sicurezza Energetica. (2023a). *PIANO NAZIONALE INTEGRATO PER L'ENERGIA E IL CLIMA*.
- Ministero dell'Ambiente e della Sicurezza Energetica. (n.d.). *Operational guidelines for the Environmental Impact Assessment Procedure - Environmental Assessments and Authorizations - SEA - EIA - IPPC Permit*. Retrieved June 20, 2024, from <https://va.mite.gov.it/en-GB/ps/comunicazione/indicazionioperativevia>
- Ministero dell'Ambiente e della Sicurezza Energetica. (2023b). *Piano individuazione aree idonee selezione siti di stoccaggio geologico della CO2 | Ministero dell'Ambiente e della Sicurezza Energetica*.
- Newman, N., Fletcher, R., Robertson, C. T., Eddy, K., & Nielsen, R. K. (2023). *Reuters Institute Digital News Report 2022*. <https://doi.org/10.60625/risj-x1gn-m549>
- OECD. (2022). *The Culture Fix: Creative people, places and industries. Local Economic and Employment Development (LEED)*. OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/19901097>
- Oltra, C., Preuß, S., Germán, S., Wesche, J., Dütschke, E., & Prades, A. (2020). *Stakeholders' views on CCUS developments in the studied regions* (STRATEGY CCUS WP3 Deliverable D3.2). https://www.strategyccus.eu/sites/default/files/D3.2_Stakeholders%E2%80%99%20views%20on%20CCUS%20developments%20in%20the%20studied%20regions_wDraftNote.pdf

- Oltra, C., Sala, R., & Boso, À. (2012). The influence of information on individuals' reactions to CCS technologies: Results from experimental online survey research. *Greenhouse Gases: Science and Technology*, 2(3), 209–215. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ghg.1285>
- Parmiter, P., & Bell, R. (2020). *Public perception of CCS: A Review of Public Engagement for CCS Projects: 2 2nd Report of the Thematic Working Group on: Policy, regulation and public perception*. https://ccuszen.eu/sites/default/files/TG1_Briefing-Report-Public-Perception-of-CCS.pdf
- Pietzner, K., Schumann, D., Tvedt, S. D., Torvatn, H. Y., Næss, R., Reiner, D. M., Anghel, S., Cismaru, D., Constantin, C., Daamen, D. D., Dudu, A., Esken, A., Gemeni, V., Ivan, L., Koukouzas, N., Kristiansen, G., Markos, A., ter Mors, E., Nihfidov, O. C., . . . Ziogou, F. (2011). Public awareness and perceptions of carbon dioxide capture and storage (CCS): Insights from surveys administered to representative samples in six European countries. *Energy Procedia*, 4, 6300–6306. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2011.02.645>
- Preuß, S., Dütschke, E., Oltra, C., Goncales, L., Prades, A., & Germán, S. (2022). *Stakeholder engagement findings: Roadmap and final recommendations* (STRATEGY CCUS WP3 Deliverable D3.4).
- Regional Policy for Greece Post-2020*. (2020). OECD. <https://doi.org/10.1787/cedf09a5-en>
- Regione Emilia-Romagna. (n.d.). *Regione Emilia-Romagna*. Retrieved June 20, 2024, from <https://www.regione.emilia-romagna.it/>
- Regione Emilia-Romagna. (2020). *Elezioni regionali 2020 Riepilogo Emilia-Romagna*. <https://wwwservizi.regione.emilia-romagna.it/elezioni2020/>
- Regione Emilia-Romagna. (2024a). *Earthquakes of May 2012*. <https://ambiente.regione.emilia-romagna.it/en/geologia/seismic-risk/earthquake-20-may-2012>
- Regione Emilia-Romagna. (2024b). *Seismic risk in Emilia-Romagna*. <https://ambiente.regione.emilia-romagna.it/en/geologia/seismic-risk>
- Regione Emilia-Romagna. (2024c). *Turismo, 2023 record per l'Emilia-Romagna: 62 milioni di presenze e 14,5 milioni di arrivi - Regione Emilia-Romagna*. <https://www.regione.emilia-romagna.it/notizie/2024/febbraio/turismo-2023-record-per-lemiliaromagna>
- Ricerche Industriali ed Energetiche. (2015). *Territorio e Idrocarburi in Emilia-Romagna: Quaderno di approfondimento*. https://www.assorisorse.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/Cahier-Emilia-Romagna-Quaderno-E-R_per_STAMPA.pdf
- Snelson, C. L. (2016). Qualitative and Mixed Methods Social Media Research: A Review of the Literature. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 15(1).
- Spini, M. (2023). *"We are the resistance" - Fridays for Future Italy and the fight for climate justice*.
- Statista. (2023a). *Italy: employment rate by region 2023 | Statista*. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/586962/employment-rate-by-region-italy/>
- Statista. (2023b). *Italy: quarterly employment rate | Statista*. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/629035/employment-rate-quarterly-italy/>
- Statista. (2024a). *Earnings and wages in Italy*. <https://www.statista.com/topics/7167/earnings-and-wages-in-italy/#topicOverview>
- Statista. (2024b). *Italy - Gross domestic product (GDP) per capita 2029 | Statista*. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/263595/gross-domestic-product-gdp-per-capita-in-italy/>
- Statista. (2024c). *Italy: average annual gross salary by region 2023 | Statista*. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/708972/average-annual-nominal-wages-of-employees-italy-by-region/>
- Statista. (2024d). *Italy: GDP per capita by region 2022 | Statista*. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/658274/gross-domestic-product-gdp-per-capita-of-italy-by-region/>

- Stavrianakis, K., Nielsen, J., & Morrison, Z. (2024). *Public perception and acceptance of CCUS: preliminary findings of a qualitative case study in Greece: [unpublished]*. <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/articles/3-205/v2>
- Stylidis, D., & Terzidou, M. (2014). Tourism and the economic crisis in Kavala, Greece. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 44, 210–226. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.annals.2013.10.004>
- Tadini, C. (2023, November 20). Qualità della vita, la classifica: Ravenna più povera, meno in salute e sempre la peggiore per i furti in casa. *RavennaToday*. <https://www.ravennatoday.it/cronaca/qualita-vita-classifica-italia-oggi-2022-analisi-ravenna.html>
- Tcvetkov, P., Cherepovitsyn, A., & Fedoseev, S. (2019). Public perception of carbon capture and storage: A state-of-the-art overview. *Heliyon*, 5(12), e02845. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2019.e02845>
- Times Higher Education. (n.d.). *University of Bologna*. Retrieved May 29, 2024, from <https://www.timeshighereducation.com/world-university-rankings/university-bologna>
- Upham, P., Oltra, C., & Boso, À. (2015). Towards a cross-paradigmatic framework of the social acceptance of energy systems. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 8, 100–112. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2015.05.003>
- van der Zwaan, B., Broecks, K., & Dalla Longa, F. (2022). Deployment of CO₂ capture and storage in Europe under limited public acceptance—An energy system perspective. *Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions*, 45, 200–213. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eist.2022.10.004>
- Wood Water Wild. (n.d.). *Home - Wood Water Wild*. Retrieved June 20, 2024, from <https://woodwaterwild.gr/>
- WWF (2021). *Ambiguità, rischi e illusioni della CCS-CCUS: Criticità connesse allo sviluppo in Italia di una tecnologia più rischiosa che utile*. https://www.wwf.it/uploads/Report-CCS_WWF_def-impaginato-25-ott-def.pdf
- Εφορεία Αρχαιοτήτων Καβάλας. (2024, March 27). *Χάρτης σημείων ενδιαφέροντος της ΕΦ.Α.ΚΑΒ. | ΕΦΑΚΑΒ*. <https://www.efakav.gr/poi/>
- Ζορμπά, Ν. (2023, July 14). Γιατί είναι σημαντικές οι δύο πρώτες μεγάλες επενδύσεις δέσμευσης και αποθήκευσης CO₂ - Πως συνδέονται με τον Πρίνο. *Energymag.Gr*. https://www.energymag.gr/epikairoτητα/epiheiriseis/78387_giati-einai-simantikes-oi-dyo-protos-megales-ependyseis-desmeysis
- ΚΕΝΤΡΙΚΗ ΕΝΩΣΗ ΕΠΙΜΕΛΗΤΗΡΙΩΝ ΕΛΛΑΔΟΣ. (2024, June 20). *ΜΑΡΤΟΣ ΝΙΚΟΛΑΟΣ ΤΟΥ ΓΕΩΡΓΙΟΥ*. <https://publicity.businessportal.gr/company/20282730000>
- Περιβαλλοντική Κίνηση Θάσου. (n.d.). *Περιβαλλοντική Κίνηση Θάσου*. Retrieved June 20, 2024, from <https://thassosnature.wordpress.com/>

8 ANNEX: REPORTING TEMPLATES

8.1 DOCUMENT ANALYSIS: REPORTING TEMPLATE

For the document analysis you gather information material to answer the questions/ points provided in the tables below. The information is divided into six different parts (3.1 – 3.6)

1. geographical factors and location characteristics
2. governance of the region and administrative factors
3. socio-demographic factors
4. perceptions
5. key actors
6. other information you find important

1. GEOGRAPHICAL FACTORS AND LOCATION CHARACTERISTICS

The following table aims at gathering information about geographical factors (such as proximity to protected areas) and characteristics of the area (such as prominence of industry).

CATEGORY	QUESTIONS	FINDINGS	SOURCE
geographic make-up of the region	<i>Please describe/ explain the geographic make-up of the area, such as the size of the affected municipalities/regions, where and how they have coastal boundaries and where and how they might have other boundaries (proximity to mountains, other countries, etc...)</i>		
Protected areas	<i>Are there any protected areas in the affected region or close by (e.g. natural or geological heritage sites, Natura 2000 areas)? If so, are they affected by CCUS plans and/or HERCCULES?</i>		
Culture	<i>Heritage sites: Are there any cultural heritage sites in the area?</i>		
	<i>Does the coast or sea have a special meaning to the people living in the area (e.g. sport, recreational area, religious area, longstanding tradition of fishing)?</i>		
Location characteristics	<i>Is the area more urban or rural? Where are larger cities located and what cities are those?</i>		
	<i>How is the infrastructure in the region? Is the region rather isolated or well connected with other parts of the country (e.g. highways, railway; settlements, roads, transport options, health and educational services)?</i>		

	<i>What is the proximity to the next universities?</i>		
Seismic activity	<i>Is there seismic activity in the region? If yes, please describe.</i>		
Industry	<i>Please, describe the industry in the area, such as: what industrial sites/companies are located in or near the affected area? What is their contribution of these industrial companies to employment in the region and the national GDP? Does the region have a tradition of industrial companies/ actions? (for fossil fuel companies also see the next question)</i>		
	<i>Fossil fuel extraction in the area: What is being extracted? By which companies? When did fossil fuel extraction begin in the region? How has fossil fuel extraction developed (e.g., has it decreased in recent years)?</i>		
	<i>Are there any relevant experiences with renewable-energy infrastructure projects in the past/present?</i>		
Economy	<i>Please, describe the overall economic situation of the region. Does the region have a strong or weak economy compared to other regions/ the country overall?</i>		
	<i>Please describe relevant economic sectors in the area. For instance, look into: What are relevant economic sectors (e.g. fishing, tourism)? How do they contribute to the region's economy? Are the sectors relevant for the income in the area? Are the economic activities/ sectors rather new or do they have a long tradition)? Could they be in conflict with CCUS?</i>		
Unique selling point	<i>Why was the region chosen for CCUS? What differentiates the region from other regions?</i>		

2. GOVERNANCE OF THE REGION AND ADMINISTRATIVE FACTORS

The following table concentrates on the governance and administration of the region and decarbonisation/ CCUS.

CATEGORY	QUESTIONS	FINDINGS	SOURCE
Administration	<i>In which state/ other administrative unit is the affected region located?</i>		
	<i>How does the administration function? Are the municipalities/ regions/ states</i>		

	<i>autonomous from national governments? Is the governance structure centralized or decentralized? What are the municipalities' responsibilities and duties vis-a-vis industry, civil society, and other stakeholders?</i>		
Political parties	<i>Please, describe important political parties. You could look at: What are important political parties (on the national/ regional level)? Is this similar for the national and regional level? Is their influence stable or does it change (e.g. you could look at the development in last 10 years)?</i>		
Governance of decarbonisation and CCUS	<i>Who sets basic regulations and/or laws for decarbonisation and CCUS in the region concerned? Does this happen more on a national level, on a regional level?</i>		
	<i>What are important regulations regarding decarbonisation and/ or CCUS on the regional level? How did the regulation develop in the last years (you could look at the last 20 years)?</i>		
	<i>Are there any policy or administrative requirements to involve the public in infrastructure decision-making? Are there social and environmental feasibility studies that need to be conducted and implemented? By whom, when and how?</i>		

3. SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC FACTORS

The following table concentrates on describing the population in the area.

Often, statistics used to describe the population are provided for specific regions. Therefore, make sure to indicate which regions the data provided refers to.			
CATEGORY	QUESTIONS	FINDINGS	SOURCE
Population	<p><i>Please, describe the population of the region. You can look into: How many people live in the affected region? What is the population density in the regions? How does the population size develop (e.g. In-migration and out-migration; e.g. changes from 2000)?</i></p> <p><i>Is the population density and development similar to the situation in Italy/Greece as a whole?</i></p>		

	<p><i>What is the age distribution of the population? You can look e.g. for aging index or the share of people in working age. Did the age distribution change (e.g. changes from 2000)?</i></p> <p><i>Is the distribution and development similar to the situation in Italy/Greece as a whole?</i></p>		
	<p><i>What is the gender distribution in the region?</i></p> <p><i>How is this in comparison to Italy/Greece as a whole?</i></p>		
Employment	<p><i>Please, describe the employment situation in the region, such as: What is the employment rate/ unemployment rate in the region? How did the employment situation develop (you could look for developments in the last 20 years)?</i></p> <p><i>How is this in comparison to Italy/Greece as a whole?</i></p>		
	<p><i>Please, describe the income and wealth situation in the region. For instance, you could look at: What is the average monthly earning by employees? What is the per capita spending power in the region?</i></p> <p><i>How is this in comparison to Italy/Greece as a whole?</i></p>		
Housing	<p><i>How many people own their homes compared to rented properties in the region? What is the share of secondary homes? What is the average value of property purchased in the region?</i></p> <p><i>How is this in comparison to Italy/Greece as a whole?</i></p>		
Education	<p><i>Please, describe the educational structure in the region. You could look at: What is the distribution of educational degrees in the region? How did the educational structure develop (e.g. in the last 20 years)?</i></p>		

	<i>How is this in comparison to Italy/Greece as a whole?</i>		
--	--	--	--

4. PERCEPTIONS

This table concentrates on perception by the public and other actors.

CATEGORY	QUESTIONS	FINDINGS	SOURCE
Perception of CCUS	<i>Please, describe the culture of environmentalism, conservationism or public protest: Is there a strong culture in the region? Are there any groups or individuals opposing industrial projects, oil & gas or CCUS in the region? If so, what are their concerns?</i>		
	<i>Are there any other groups or individuals, such as scientists or associations that have a position on CCUS? Do they comment negatively/positively on CCUS in general and the storage projects in particular? What are their arguments?</i>		
	<i>According to the document analysis, can you already assess and describe public perception or community concerns regarding CCUS? Are there existing studies or reports on this?</i>		
Perception decarbonisation	<i>How is decarbonisation perceived in the region in general? Is it discussed within the public? Is it perceived to be important?</i>		
Company perception	<i>How are the storage company's activities (not just CCUS) perceived in the region? Is the company an important player (in terms of business, lobbying)?</i>		
Perception of risks	<i>Have there been any industrial incidents (e.g. oil/gas spills), seismic activities or CCUS activities that have been risky or have been perceived to be risky in the past or the present? <i>If yes, please explain.</i></i>		

5. KEY ACTORS

The aim of this table is to summarize the key actors. You could identify key actors by checking who provides information material on CCUS/ who writes about CCUS in the documents.

CATEGORY	QUESTIONS	FINDINGS	SOURCE
Administration/ governance	<i>Are there any other governmental/ administrative actors important for the region in general and CCUS in particular (besides the information you already provided in Table 3.2)? Why are they important? Can they have an influence on the project/ the advances or governance of CCUS?</i>		
Economy	<i>Are there any other economic actors (such as interest groups) or companies important for the region in general and CCUS in particular (besides the information you already provided in Table 3.1)? Why are they important? Can they have an influence on the project/ the advances or governance of CCUS?</i>		
Research and universities	<i>Are there any research institutions/ universities playing a role in the region in general and for CCUS in particular? Why are they playing a role? Can they have an influence on the project/ the advances or governance of CCUS?</i>		
Other actors key	<i>Are there any (other) environmental actors, NGOs, other interest groups or individuals playing a role in the region in general and for CCUS in particular (besides the information you already provided in 3.4)? Why are they playing a role? Can they have an influence on the project/ the advances or governance of CCUS?</i>		

6. OTHER INFORMATION YOU FIND IMPORTANT

CATEGORY	QUESTIONS	FINDINGS	SOURCE
...

8.2 MEDIA ANALYSIS REPORTING TEMPLATES

1. REPORTING PRESS ANALYSIS

A) What are recurring/dominant topics / how is CCUS framed?	<input type="checkbox"/> Decarbonisation <input type="checkbox"/> Climate change <input type="checkbox"/> Mitigation vs. Adaptation <input type="checkbox"/> Technology <input type="checkbox"/> Risks <input type="checkbox"/> ...	
	Please summarize the most frequent /dominant framings in your own words.	
	Can you observe a change in framing over time? Please describe.	
	Can you observe a change in framing among different media sources? Please describe	
B) Please list the most frequent/relevant national and regional stakeholders in the media sources (across business, civil society, policy, media)	<input type="checkbox"/> ... <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> ... <input type="checkbox"/> ... <input type="checkbox"/> ...	
	Are these stakeholders mentioned in the media articles or are they the authors of the articles?	
	Can you observe a change of stakeholders over time?	

2. REPORTING STAKEHOLDER-DRIVEN ANALYSIS OF FACEBOOK AND LINKEDIN POSTS

A) What are recurring/dominant topics / how is CCUS framed across the posts?	<input type="checkbox"/> Decarbonisation <input type="checkbox"/> Climate change <input type="checkbox"/> Mitigation vs. Adaptation <input type="checkbox"/> Technology <input type="checkbox"/> Risks <input type="checkbox"/> ...	
	Please summarize the most frequent /dominant framings in your own words.	

	Can you observe a change in framing over time? Please describe.	
	Can you observe a change in framing among different stakeholders? Please describe	
	Can you observe a difference between Facebook and LinkedIn posts?	

3. REPORTING COUNTRY-SPECIFIC SEARCH ON GOOGLE AND YOUTUBE

- Please take screenshots of the complete result page for each search query AND save the page as a PDF
- Google

Please fill this table for each of the search queries:

Search term: XYZ		
Is Google directly presenting information extracted from other pages? (From what pages? what information is extracted?)		
Is Google providing questions and answers on the topic? (What questions, what sources are used to answer the questions?)		
Is Google providing alternative search terms? (What are the alternative search terms provided?)		
Is Google promoting different kinds of content? (Videos, news bars, etc.)		
For each link on the first Google page, please indicate:	LINK	
	Source (private company, ONG, newspaper, academia, policy, etc.)	
	Type of content (news article, website page, academic study, etc.)	
	Content analysis (what is the topic/frame - overall positive/negative, etc.)	

- YouTube

Please fill this table for each of the search queries:

Search term: XYZ		
For each link on the first Youtube page, please indicate:	LINK	
	Source (private company, ONG, media, academia, policy, etc.)	
	Type of content (news, documentary, campaign video, educational video)	
	Content analysis (what is the topic/frame - overall positive/negative, etc.)	

8.3 STAKEHOLDER INTERVIEWS: SUMMARY REPORT TEMPLATE

Please provide a summary report for each of the conducted stakeholder interviews.

Interview # _____

Stakeholder category _____

Stakeholder organization _____

A) CCUS Perceptions (own)

*What were the main expectations/vision in regard to CCUS in the regions?
What were the main concerns?*

Who shares the same visions/expectations? Who disagrees and why?

B) CCUS Perceptions (others)

Is the topic of CCUS discussed widely in the region? Why or why not? What is the general narrative of the discussion? Are there differences in the tone of discussion depending who talks about it (policy, industry, community?)

C) Actors/Stakeholders:

Who are the actors/stakeholders who are involved in CCUS activities in the region? Are these actors perceived as constructive in their involvement? Why or why not? (Optional: other CCUS projects?)

Who is currently not involved in the discussion / in ongoing activities but should be involved in the future? Why?

Role of media in the region

D) Policies & Regulations

What are policies or regulations the interviewed stakeholder knows about/uses in everyday working life when it comes to the development and implementation of CCUS activities in the region? Are there any regulations missing?

Additional Comments / Interesting Findings from the Interview